

Appendix 1: Technical sheets of the plant health indicators (phytosanitary situation).

PHI1: Mandatory notification of plant diseases and harmful organisms			
Description: The number of notifications received by the FASFC each year with regards to the detection of plant diseases and harmful organisms (excluding control plan).			
Results:			
Year	Number of notifications	% conformity	Limit
2010	25	Not applicable	Not applicable
2009	23	Not applicable	Not applicable
2008	43	Not applicable	Not applicable
2007	12	Not applicable	Not applicable
Calculation of the indicator: Compared to 2009, there was an increase of 8.70 % in 2010. Compared to 2008, there was a reduction of 46.51% in 2009. Compared to 2007, there was an increase of 258.33 % in 2008.			
Interpretation: This indicator demonstrates that operators in the plant production chain, including other individuals (professionals), are alert and that they comply with the legal requirements by notifying the FASFC when they identify a plant or plant product that shows a phytosanitary risk. An increase of the indicator thus implies that vigilance with respect to the phytosanitary situation in Belgium has improved.			
Part of the chain to which the indicator applies: Primary plant production, plant and plant product trading (including imports/exports), plant propagation.			
Type of plant or plant product: Plants and plant products.			
Category: Crisis prevention and management			
Justification for the selection of this indicator: The presence on the Belgian territory of harmful quarantine organisms can be extremely detrimental, economically speaking, to plant and plant product production. Crisis prevention and management via mandatory notification is essential for maintaining or improving the phytosanitary situation.			
Additional information: Each and every operator carrying out activities that fall under the competence of the FASFC is required to inform the FASFC of any suspicion or reason to assume that a product that was imported, produced, grown, processed, manufactured or distributed by it constitutes a potential health hazard for plants. Each and every laboratory or inspection or certification body must immediately inform the FASFC in the event of the slightest suspicion that a product that was put on the market does not meet the phytosanitary safety recommendations.			
Legal framework:			
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Council Directive 2000/29/EC of 8/05/2000 on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community. 2. Regulation (EC) N° 690/2008 recognising protected zones exposed to particular plant health risks in the Community. 3. Royal decree of 19/11/1987 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products. 4. Royal decree of 10/08/2005 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products. 5. Ministerial decree of 4/07/1996 establishing the conditions under which certain harmful organisms, plants, plant products or other objects listed in appendices I to V of the Royal Decree of 3/05/1994 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products, may be introduced or moved within the Community or certain protected zones thereof for trial or scientific purposes or for work on varietal selection. 6. Royal Decree of 14/11/2003 concerning self-checking, compulsory notification and traceability in the food chain. 7. Ministerial decree of 22/01/2004 on the modalities regarding the mandatory notification within the food chain. 			
Does the indicator meet the set criteria?:			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Measureable (availability of quantitative data) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Independent (no overlap between respective indicators) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reliable (bias sensitivity) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Availability of information contained in existing reports or documents <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Relevancy with respect to the health situation of plant production <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Clear interpretation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sustainable <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> The body of indicators must be representative of the plant and plant product production chain			

Comments: This indicator concerns notifications relating to non-official samples, i.e. samples that were not taken by the FASFC and thus not within the framework of the FASFC control plan. Should the number of notifications drop, this does not necessarily mean that the situation has improved. In fact, this could relate to a situation in which a harmful organism has managed to establish itself on the territory has started to spread (endemic) despite control measures and the eradication of which is no longer possible. Notifications in such cases would have less (or little) consequence.

Explanatory notes to the results: The increase in the number of notifications in 2008 is in response to a higher number of outbreaks of fireblight resulting from weather conditions that favour the development of fireblight and, due to an intensive awareness campaign that was conducted on the subject of fireblight in the province of West Flanders. However, since 2010, the operators registered with the Agency who are taking adequate control measures (pruning up to 50 cm below the lowest infection site, cutting at ground level or removing any host plant infected by the organism and neighbouring plants) and who refer to the presence of harmful organisms in their register, no longer need to notify the presence of fireblight to the provincial control unit (PCU) of the FASFC.

PHI2: Self-checking for plant production			
Description: The percentage of annual key activities performed (see Appendix 4) with a validated/certified self-checking system (SCS) in the plant production sector.			
Results:			
Year	Number of key activities performed	% of key activities performed with a validated/certified self-checking system	Limit
2010	47,959	42.76 %	Not applicable
2009	45,870	30.97 %	Not applicable
2008	45,752	18.96 %	Not applicable
2007	42,560	12.12 %	Not applicable
Calculation of the indicator: Compared to 2009, there was an increase of 38.07 % in 2010. Compared to 2008, there was an increase of 63.34 % in 2009. Compared to 2007, there was an increase of 56.44 % in 2008.			
Interpretation: This indicator serves as a criterion for the percentage of key activities for which a validated/certified SCS (self-checking system) is available. A validated/certified SCS is an SCS that has been declared to be in conformity with the set of requirements after investigation by a third party (FASFC or a certification body). An independently validated/certified SCS enhances its added value and makes it more trustworthy with regard to its foundations and functioning. An increase of the percentage of key activities with a validated/certified self-checking system thus indirectly leads to a higher confidence level with regard to adequate preventive actions taken in order to ensure overall plant health.			
Part of the chain to which the indicator applies: Primary production suppliers, primary plant production, plant and plant product trading (including imports/exports), plant propagation.			
Type of plant or plant product: Plants and plant products.			
Category: Development of self-checking			
Justification for the selection of this indicator: Self-checking constitutes an important policy instrument for achieving/maintaining a high level of preventive safeguarding with respect to plant health. During the validation/certification process, the SCS is put to the test in order to see whether or not it is in conformity with the set requirements. The percentage of key activities with a validated/certified SCS serves as an indication as to the presence of a properly functioning self-checking system.			
Additional information: Self-checking stands for the entire set of measures that are taken by the operators in order to ensure that all products falling under their responsibility, and for all production, processing and distribution phases, are capable of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • meeting the legal requirements regarding plant health; • meeting the legal requirements regarding product quality, for which the FASFC is responsible; • meeting the requirements regarding the traceability and monitoring of the effective compliance of these requirements. On the basis of a sector guide, companies can have their SCS certified by a certification or inspection body (OCI) that has been recognised as such by the FASFC. In the event where there is no approved guide available for a certain sector, or if no OCI has been approved by the FASFC, the operator may call upon the FASFC to conduct the validation.			
Legal framework: The validation/certification of the SCS does not represent a legal requirement. The legal framework regarding self-checking and the use of sector guides can be found in the following legal texts: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Royal Decree of 14 November 2003 concerning self-checking, compulsory notification and traceability in the food chain. 			
Does the indicator meet the set criteria?: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Measureable (availability of quantitative data) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Independent (no overlap between respective indicators) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reliable (bias sensitivity) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Availability of information contained in existing reports or documents <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Relevancy with respect to the health situation of plant production <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Clear interpretation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sustainable 			

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> The body of indicators must be representative of the plant and plant product production chain
Comments: Operators may freely decide whether or not to have their self-checking system validated/certified. A key activity, for which no validated/certified self-checking system is available, does not mean that the self-checking system is absent or that it does not function correctly. However, validation by a third party enhances its value and credibility as it is done independently.
Explanatory notes to the results: /
Key Activities: In Appendix 4 the activities are listed that have been selected as key activities of the activity tree structure. The number of key activities performed means the total number of key activities performed (see Appendix 4) by all operators in the plant production sector in Belgium.

PHI3: Phytosanitary inspections (physical checks)

Description: The percentage of annual phytosanitary inspections that were deemed to be favourable or favourable, subject to remarks.

Results:

Year	Number of physical phytosanitary inspections	% favourable or favourable with remarks	Limit
2010	3,106	96.4 %	Not applicable
2009	3,395	95.3 %	Not applicable
2008	3,034	95.2 %	Not applicable
2007	2,773	94.6 %	Not applicable

Calculation of the indicator: Compared to 2009, there was an increase of 1.15 % in 2010. Compared to 2008, there was an increase of 0.11 % in 2009. Compared to 2007, there was an increase of 0.63 % in 2008.

Interpretation: This indicator measures the extent to which the operators have met the legal requirements concerning plant health. An increase of this indicator is associated with an improvement of the phytosanitary situation in Belgium.

Part of the chain to which the indicator applies: Primary production suppliers, primary plant production, plant and plant product trading (including imports/exports), plant propagation, green spaces and forests.

Type of plant or plant product: All plant production but mainly agricultural, garden and ornamental plants intended for planting.

Category: Control.

Justification for the selection of this indicator: The presence on the Belgian territory of harmful quarantine organisms can be extremely detrimental, economically speaking, to plant and plant product production. It is therefore essential to maintain/improve the phytosanitary situation by verifying the absence of these organisms.

Additional information: The list of plants and plant products inspected is shown in the 2023 PPV check-list (http://www.afsca.be/checklists-fr/_documents/FAVVChecklist-2023v3fr.pdf).

Legal framework:

1. Council Directive 2000/29/EC of 8/05/2000 on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community.
2. Regulation (EC) N° 690/2008 recognising protected zones exposed to particular plant health risks in the Community.
3. Royal decree of 19 November 1987 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products.
4. Royal decree of 10 August 2005 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products.
5. Ministerial decree of 4/07/1996 establishing the conditions under which certain harmful organisms, plants, plant products or other objects listed in appendices I to V of the Royal Decree of 3/05/1994 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products, may be introduced or moved within the Community or certain protected zones thereof for trial or scientific purposes or for work on varietal selection.

Does the indicator meet the set criteria?:

- Measureable (availability of quantitative data)
- Independent (no overlap between respective indicators)
- Reliable (bias sensitivity)
- Availability of information contained in existing reports or documents
- Relevancy with respect to the health situation of plant production
- Clear interpretation
- Sustainable
- The body of indicators must be representative of the plant and plant product production chain

Comments: The result of an inspection is determined on the basis of a checklist, whereby a fixed appraisal is given, in the form of a points score, for each item to be controlled and in accordance with its importance. As for the results of any inspection, there are three possibilities: either favourable, favourable with remarks or unfavourable. The latter will result in taking further measures or in the

drawing up of a report.

Explanatory notes to the results: It is difficult to compare the results of 2008 with those of 2007, as the FASFC has been implementing a new evaluation system since 2007. This system is based on the use of a checklist, by which a fixed appraisal is made, in the form of a points score, for each item to be controlled and in accordance with its importance. Although this new evaluation method is more stringent and accounts for at least part of the differences, clearly there remains some room for improvement. Part of the explanation may also lie in the fact that inspections have been focusing on establishments where non-conformities have been found before (systematic re-inspection).

PHI4: Phytosanitary inspections (traceability)			
Description: The percentage of annual phytosanitary inspections relating to traceability that were deemed to be favourable or favourable, subject to remarks.			
Results:			
Year	Number of phytosanitary inspections relating to traceability	% favourable or favourable with remarks	Limit
2010	1,101	98.0 %	Not applicable
2009	1,104	95.6 %	Not applicable
2008	776	96.2 %	Not applicable
2007	727	94 %	Not applicable
Calculation of the indicator: Compared to 2009, there was an increase of 2.51 % in 2010. Compared to 2008, there was a reduction of 0.62 % in 2009. Compared to 2007, there was an increase of 2.34 % in 2008.			
Interpretation: This indicator measures the extent to which operators have met the legal requirements concerning traceability with regards to plant health. An increase of this indicator is associated with an indirect improvement of the phytosanitary situation in Belgium.			
Part of the chain to which the indicator applies: Primary production suppliers, primary plant production, plant and plant product trading (including imports/exports), plant propagation.			
Type of plant or plant product: All plant production but mainly ornamental plants, potatoes and plants.			
Category: Control.			
Justification for the selection of this indicator: The presence on the Belgian territory of harmful quarantine organisms can be extremely detrimental, economically speaking, to plant and plant product production. It is therefore of utmost importance to check, on the one hand, the data relating to incoming and outgoing plant passports and on the other the plants and plant products received and shipped, with the objective of indirectly maintaining/improving the phytosanitary situation.			
Additional information: Traceability means the ability to trace and monitor products through the various production, processing and distribution phases.			
Legal framework:			
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Council Directive 2000/29/EC of 8/05/2000 on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community. 2. Regulation (EC) N° 690/2008 recognising protected zones exposed to particular plant health risks in the Community. 3. Royal decree of 19/11/1987 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products. 4. Royal decree of 10/08/2005 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products. 5. Ministerial decree of 4/07/1996 establishing the conditions under which certain harmful organisms, plants, plant products or other objects listed in appendices I to V of the Royal Decree of 3/05/1994 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products, may be introduced, or moved within the Community or certain protected zones thereof for trial or scientific purposes or for work on varietal selection. 6. Royal Decree of 14/11/2003 concerning self-checking, compulsory notification and traceability in the food chain. 			
Does the indicator meet the set criteria?:			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Measureable (availability of quantitative data) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Independent (no overlap between respective indicators) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reliable (bias sensitivity) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Availability of information contained in existing reports or documents <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Relevancy with respect to the health situation of plant production <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Clear interpretation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sustainable <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> The body of indicators must be representative of the plant and plant product production chain			
Comments: The result of an inspection is determined on the basis of a checklist, whereby a fixed appraisal is given, in the form of a points score, for each item to be controlled and in accordance with its importance. As for the results of any inspection, there are three possibilities: either favourable, favourable with remarks or unfavourable. The latter will result in taking further measures or in the			

drawing up of a report.

Explanatory notes to the results: It is difficult to compare the results of 2008 with those of 2007, as the FASFC has been implementing a new evaluation system since 2007. This system is based on the use of a checklist, by which a fixed appraisal is made, in the form of a points score, for each item to be controlled and in accordance with its importance. Although this new evaluation method is more stringent and accounts for at least part of the differences, clearly there remains some room for improvement. Part of the explanation may also lie in the fact that inspections have been focusing on establishments where non-conformities have been found before (systematic re-inspection). In 2007, the results were divided into 2 categories: "Administrative plant health check" and "Traceability (including identification and registration)". The results for 2007 were respectively 193 inspections with 93.3 % conformity for the 1st category and 534 inspections with 94.3 % conformity for the second category. For 2008, these 2 categories were combined.

PHI5: Harmful organisms regulated and detected in Belgium

Description: The percentage of regulated harmful organisms for which at least one sample is tested positive per year in Belgium in relation to the total number of regulated harmful organisms.

Results:

Year	Number of different harmful organisms detected	% in relation to the total number of regulated harmful organisms	Limit
2010	15	6.64 %	Not applicable
2009	15	6.64 %	Not applicable
2008	14	6.39 %	Not applicable
2007	12	5.45 %	Not applicable

Calculation of the indicator: Compared to 2009, there was no change in 2010. Compared to 2008, there was an increase of 3.91 % in 2009. Compared to 2007, there was an increase of 17.25 % in 2008.

Interpretation: This indicator measures the extent to which plants and plant products are subject to the pressure of harmful quarantine organisms. An increase of this indicator is associated with a deterioration of the plant health situation in Belgium.

Part of the chain to which the indicator applies: Primary production suppliers, primary plant production, plant and plant product trading (including imports/exports), plant propagation, green spaces and forests.

Type of plant or plant product: All plants and plant products.

Category: Development of self-checking and Control.

Justification for the selection of this indicator: The presence on the Belgian territory of harmful quarantine organisms can be extremely detrimental, economically speaking, to plant and plant product production and to international trade. It is therefore essential to follow this parameter carefully and to eventually take the necessary control measures, with the objective of maintaining/improving the phytosanitary situation.

Additional information: -

Legal framework:

- Royal decree of 10/08/2005 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products.

Does the indicator meet the set criteria?:

- Measureable (availability of quantitative data)
- Independent (no overlap between respective indicators)
- Reliable (bias sensitivity)
- Availability of information contained in existing reports or documents
- Relevancy with respect to the health situation of plant production
- Clear interpretation
- Sustainable
- The body of indicators must be representative of the plant and plant product production chain

Comments: Regulated harmful organisms detected during phytosanitary import controls are not included in this indicator.

Harmful organisms that are exclusively regulated for protected EU zones are not covered by this indicator either (i.e. solely those covered in part B of the Royal Decree of 10/08/2005, and not those listed in the other parts or sections).

The harmful organisms listed in the Royal Decree of 19/11/1987 for which no active control policy has been conducted are not covered either.

Explanatory notes to the results: In 2010, 15 different species of harmful organisms were detected at least on one occasion on the Belgian territory (new in comparison with 2009: *Oligonychus perditus*, *Clavibacter michiganensis* ssp. *michiganensis*, *Xanthomonas fragariae*, *Chrysanthemum stunt viroid*, *Tomato spotted wilt virus*) out of a total of 226 regulated species.

In 2009, 15 different species of harmful organisms were detected at least on one occasion on the Belgian territory (new in comparison with 2008: *Liriomyza trifolii*, *Ditylenchus dipsaci*, *Clavibacter michiganensis* ssp. *sepedonicus*, *Ralstonia solanacearum*, *Apple proliferation mycoplasma*) out of a total of 226 regulated species.

In 2008, 14 different species of harmful organisms were detected at least on one occasion on the Belgian territory (new in comparison with 2007: *Anoplophora glabripennis*, *Puccinia horiana*,

Chrysanthemum stunt viroid) out of a total of 219 regulated species.
In 2007, 12 different species of harmful organisms were detected at least on one occasion on the Belgian territory out of a total of 220 regulated species.

PHI6: Phytosanitary import controls

Description: The percentage of samples of plant and plant product consignments, imported into the EU via the Belgian border inspection posts (BIP), which are compliant with the plant health requirements.

Results:

Year	Number of samples	% conformity	Limit
2010	335	87.20 %	Not applicable
2009	395	85.57 %	Not applicable
2008	489	77.51 %	Not applicable
2007	526	83.84 %	Not applicable

Calculation of the indicator: Compared to 2009, there was an increase of 1.90 % in 2010. Compared to 2008, there was an increase of 10.40 % in 2009. Compared to 2007, there was a reduction of 7.55 % in 2008.

Interpretation: This indicator demonstrates that the active plant and plant product import operators comply with the legal requirements with respect to plant health. An increase of this indicator thus implies an improvement in the plant health situation in Belgium.

Part of the chain to which the indicator applies: Trade - imports of plant and plant products.

Type of plant or plant product: Plants and plant products.

Category: Control – Imports

Justification for the selection of this indicator: The presence on the Belgian territory of harmful quarantine organisms can be extremely detrimental, economically speaking, to plant and plant product production. It is therefore essential to maintain/improve the phytosanitary situation by verifying the absence of these organisms in the imported plants and plant products. This indicator is a measurement of the risk that Belgium faces with regards to the introduction of harmful quarantine organisms.

Additional information: All shipments entering the European Union via Belgium are presented at a Belgian border inspection post. This shipments first need to undergo a documentary check. After this, checks are made to ensure that the shipped goods tally with these documents. As a third step, a plant health check is carried out and a control sample may be taken. Sampling may be conducted within the scope of protective measures (as imposed by a decree of the European Commission) or the FASFC control plan.

Legal framework:

1. Council Directive 2000/29/EC of 8/05/2000 on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community.
2. Regulation (EC) N° 690/2008 recognising protected zones exposed to particular plant health risks in the Community.
3. Royal decree of 19/11/1987 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products.
4. Royal decree of 10/08/2005 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products.
5. Ministerial decree of 4/07/1996 establishing the conditions under which certain harmful organisms, plants, plant products or other objects listed in appendices I to V of the Royal Decree of 3/05/1994 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products, may be introduced or moved within the Community or certain protected zones thereof for trial or scientific purposes or for work on varietal selection.
6. Ministerial decree of 23 December 2004 establishing the procedure for the execution of phytosanitary import controls and the requirements relating to these controls.

Does the indicator meet the set criteria?:

- Measureable (availability of quantitative data)
- Independent (no overlap between respective indicators)
- Reliable (bias sensitivity)
- Availability of information contained in existing reports or documents
- Relevancy with respect to the health situation of plant production
- Clear interpretation
- Sustainable
- The body of indicators must be representative of the plant and plant product production chain

Comments: Controls carried out at the border inspection posts (BIP) such as Zaventem, Ostend and Bierseet airports, and the Port of Antwerp for example. A first sample set is taken to check for the

presence of symptoms, a second sample set is taken randomly and a third sample set is taken systematically.

Explanatory notes to the results: -

PHI7: <i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i> (Pine wood nematode)			
Description: The annual percentage of results that comply with the pine wood nematode control (<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>) within the framework of the FASFC control plan.			
Results:			
Year	Number of samples	% conformity	Limit
2010	178	100 %	Not applicable
2009	202	100 %	Not applicable
2008	229	100 %	Not applicable
2007	183	100 %	Not applicable
Calculation of the indicator: Compared to 2009, there was no change in 2010. Compared to 2008, there was no change in 2009. Compared to 2007, there was no change in 2008.			
Interpretation: This indicator measures the presence of pine wood nematode within the Belgian plant production chain. An increase of this indicator, i.e. an increase in the percentage of compliant samples, therefore implies an improvement in the plant health situation in Belgium.			
Part of the chain to which the indicator applies: Primary plant production, plant and plant product trading (including imports/exports), plant propagation, green spaces and forests.			
Type of plant or plant product: Sensitive wood products and conifer plants.			
Category: Control.			
Justification for the selection of this indicator: The presence on the Belgian territory of harmful quarantine organisms such as pine wood nematode can be extremely detrimental, economically speaking, to plant and plant product production. It is therefore essential to maintain/improve the plant health situation by verifying the absence of this organism.			
Additional information: <i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i> is a nematode species originating in North America and which is mainly found on <i>Pinus</i> . The dead wood of all species of pine can act as a substrate for its development. However, only a limited number of species are susceptible to attack as living trees: <i>P. densiflora</i> , <i>P. luchuensis</i> , <i>P. nigra</i> , <i>P. sylvestris</i> and <i>P. thunbergii</i> . Other conifers may also be susceptible to attack (particularly <i>Larix</i> , <i>Abies</i> and <i>Picea</i>). The main vector species of this nematode are those that belong to the genus <i>Monochamus</i> (long-horned beetle). The pine wood nematode is present in North America and Asia but absent in the EU with the exception of Portugal. Furthermore, in July 2008, the European Commission declared the whole of mainland Portugal as a demarcated area. For Portugal this means a prohibition on exporting susceptible wood products and conifer plants, except under very strict specific conditions. Following this disturbing development, the FASFC strengthened its controls. The first obvious external symptom is the yellowing and wilting of the needles, which can lead to the eventual death of the tree. The wilting may first appear on only one branch although the whole tree may later show symptoms. Further information relating to pine wood nematode is available at the following address: http://www.eppo.org/QUARANTINE/nematodes/Bursaphelenchus_xylophilus/BURSXY_ds.pdf .			
Legal framework:			
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Council Directive 2000/29/EC of 8/05/2000 on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community. 2. Commission decision 2006/133/EC of 13 February 2006 requiring Member States to temporarily take additional measures against the dissemination of <i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i> (Steiner and Buhner) Nickle <i>et al.</i> (the pine wood nematode) as regards areas in Portugal, other than those in which it is known not to occur. 3. Royal decree of 19/11/1987 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products. 4. Royal decree of 10/08/2005 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products. 5. Ministerial decree of 4/07/1996 establishing the conditions under which certain harmful organisms, plants, plant products or other objects listed in appendices I to V of the Royal Decree of 3/05/1994 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products, may be introduced or moved within the Community or certain protected zones thereof for trial or scientific purposes or for work on varietal selection. 			
Does the indicator meet the set criteria?:			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Measureable (availability of quantitative data)			13

- Independent (no overlap between respective indicators)
- Reliable (bias sensitivity)
- Availability of information contained in existing reports or documents
- Relevancy with respect to the health situation of plant production
- Clear interpretation
- Sustainable
- The body of indicators must be representative of the plant and plant product production chain

Comments: -

Explanatory notes to the results: -

PHI8: <i>Meloidogyne chitwoodi</i> and/or <i>M. fallax</i> (Root-knot nematodes)			
Description: The annual percentage of compliant results with respect to the control of root-knot nematodes (<i>Meloidogyne chitwoodi</i> and/or <i>M. fallax</i>) within the framework of the FASFC control plan.			
Results:			
Year	Number of samples	% conformity	Limit
2010	163	100 %	Not applicable
2009	162	100 %	Not applicable
2008	157	99.47 %	Not applicable
2007	Not available	Not available	Not applicable
Calculation of the indicator: Compared to 2009, there was no change in 2010. Compared to 2008, there was an increase of 0.53 % in 2009.			
Interpretation: This indicator measures the presence of root-knot nematode within the Belgian plant production chain. An increase of this indicator, i.e. an increase in the percentage of compliant samples, therefore implies an improvement in the plant health situation in Belgium.			
Part of the chain to which the indicator applies: Primary plant production, plant and plant product trading (excluding third-country imports and introduction of other EU Member States), plant propagation.			
Type of plant or plant product: Seed potatoes (survey with systematic analyses), table potatoes (visual survey with analyses in the event of symptoms), field vegetables, cereals and other crops.			
Category: Control.			
Justification for the selection of this indicator: The presence on the Belgian territory of harmful quarantine organisms such as root-knot nematodes can be extremely detrimental, economically speaking, to plant production (particularly root vegetables and tubers such as salsify, carrots, and potatoes) and plant product production. It is therefore essential to maintain/improve the phytosanitary situation by verifying the absence of these organisms.			
Additional information: In 1996-1997, it was demonstrated that <i>M. chitwoodi</i> and <i>M. fallax</i> were present in Belgium. Both nematode species infect both monocotyledons and dicotyledons and a large number of host plants, including potatoes, tomatoes, beetroots, wheat, salsify and carrots. Root-knot nematodes are characterised by the formation of nodes (root knots) on the roots. The dissemination of <i>M. chitwoodi</i> and <i>M. fallax</i> can occur through contaminated soil that adheres to agricultural machinery, through the use of contaminated propagating material, through infected plants or flower bulbs or through contaminated irrigation water. Further information relating to root-knot nematodes is available at the following address: http://www.afsca.be/productionvegetale/maladies/nematodesagalles/_documents/2008-04-14_ficheMcf_20080414_FR.pdf .			
Legal framework:			
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Council Directive 2000/29/EC of 8/05/2000 on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community. 2. Royal decree of 19/11/1987 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products. 3. Royal decree of 10/08/2005 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products. 4. Ministerial decree of 4/07/1996 establishing the conditions under which certain harmful organisms, plants, plant products or other objects listed in appendices I to V of the Royal Decree of 3/05/1994 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products, may be introduced or moved within the Community or certain protected zones thereof for trial or scientific purposes or for work on varietal selection. 			
Does the indicator meet the set criteria?:			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Measureable (availability of quantitative data) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Independent (no overlap between respective indicators) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reliable (bias sensitivity) <input type="checkbox"/> Availability of information contained in existing reports or documents <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Relevancy with respect to the health situation of plant production <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Clear interpretation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sustainable <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> The body of indicators must be representative of the plant and plant product production chain			
Comments: The figures incorporate the results of the seed potato survey, the analyses following			

visual inspections and notifications, but do not include either the results of the analyses on the extent of the contamination, their monitoring or the results relating to the control of imports and introductions. There is evidence to suggest that this harmful quarantine organism represents an emerging risk.

Explanatory notes to the results: In 2010 and 2009, although root-knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne*) were reported on various occasions with respect to field vegetable production as well as table potato production, the monitoring results illustrate that they are still absent in seed potato production zones. Annual targeted monitoring (160 samples), conducted by the Regions under the delegation also demonstrates the absence of these parasites in certified seed potatoes produced in Belgium. In 2007, a contamination of table potatoes by *Meloidogyne chitwoodi* was reported by a laboratory.

PHI9: <i>Globodera rostochiensis</i> and/or <i>G. pallida</i> (Cyst nematodes)			
Description: The annual percentage of compliant results with respect to the control of cyst nematodes (<i>Globodera rostochiensis</i> and/or <i>G. pallida</i>) within the framework of the FASFC control plan.			
Results:			
Year	Number of samples	% conformity	Limit
2010	3,235	99.07 %	Not applicable
2009	2,748	99.16 %	Not applicable
2008	2,695	99.40 %	Not applicable
2007	2,364	99.87 %	Not applicable
Calculation of the indicator: Compared to 2009, there was a reduction of 0.09 % in 2010. Compared to 2008, there was a reduction of 0.24 % in 2009. Compared to 2007, there was a reduction of 0.47 % in 2008.			
Interpretation: This indicator measures the presence of cyst nematodes within the Belgian plant propagation material production chain. An increase of this indicator, i.e. an increase in the percentage of compliant samples, therefore implies an improvement in the plant health situation in Belgium.			
Part of the chain to which the indicator applies: Primary plant production, plant and plant product trading (including imports/exports), plant propagation.			
Type of plant or plant product: Seed potatoes, table potatoes, field root vegetables and ornamental field plants with roots.			
Category: Control.			
Justification for the selection of this indicator: The presence on the Belgian territory of harmful quarantine organisms such as cyst nematodes can be extremely detrimental, economically speaking, to plant and plant product production. It is therefore essential to maintain/improve the plant health situation, by reducing its population and slowing down its growth, bearing in mind that in this particular case the presence of these harmful organisms on the Belgian territory has been demonstrated.			
Additional information: The potato is quite clearly the most significant host plant. Tomatoes and aubergines are also susceptible to attack. Other <i>Solanum</i> spp. and their hybrids may also be hosts of these <i>Globodera</i> spp. There are no specific symptoms of the attack of <i>Globodera</i> spp. Patches of poor growth within a field are often found. Dispersion is mainly in the form of cysts distributed, in order of importance, on seed potatoes, original nursery plant material, soil, flower bulbs, table or processing potatoes. The latter would only be susceptible if there is a risk with respect to their planting or if the residual soil has not been properly treated. Further information relating to cyst nematodes is available at the following address: http://www.eppo.org/QUARANTINE/nematodes/Globodera_pallida/HETDSP_ds.pdf .			
Legal framework:			
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Council Directive 2000/29/EC of 8/05/2000 on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community. 2. Royal decree of 19/11/1987 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products. 3. Royal decree of 10/08/2005 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products. 4. Royal decree of 22/06/2010 on the control of potato cyst nematodes and modifying the Royal Decree of 19 November 1987 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products. 5. Ministerial decree of 4/07/1996 establishing the conditions under which certain harmful organisms, plants, plant products or other objects listed in appendices I to V of the Royal Decree of 3/05/1994 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products, may be introduced or moved within the Community or certain protected zones thereof for trial or scientific purposes or for work on varietal selection. 			
Does the indicator meet the set criteria?:			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Measureable (availability of quantitative data) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Independent (no overlap between respective indicators) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reliable (bias sensitivity) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Availability of information contained in existing reports or documents <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Relevancy with respect to the health situation of plant production			

- Clear interpretation
- Sustainable
- The body of indicators must be representative of the plant and plant product production chain

Comments: In 2007, Europe published a new directive (2007/33/EC) on the control of potato cyst nematodes. A research project aimed at assessing the situation of this parasite on the national territory, studying its main dissemination channels and proposing methods of control was initiated in 2008.

Since 2010, 300 samples have been taken by the FASFC as part of the monitoring procedure. Prior to 2010, most of the analyses carried out were based on verifying the absence of these nematodes in plots of land used for producing nursery plants or seed potatoes (plots of land known to be contamination free or where there is a low rate of contamination). This indicator does not therefore reflect the chain approach since it only concerns plants.

Explanatory notes to the results: The 2007 figures only represent the figures submitted by the Regions.

PHI10: *Ralstonia solanacearum* and/or *Clavibacter michiganensis* subsp. *sepedonicus* (Potato brown rot and/or ring rot)

Description: The annual percentage of compliant results with respect to the control of potato brown rot and/or ring rot (*Ralstonia solanacearum* and/or *Clavibacter michiganensis* subsp. *sepedonicus*) within the framework of the FASFC control plan.

Results:

Year	Number of samples	% conformity	Limit
2010	2,476	100 %	Not applicable
2009	2,188	99.95 %	Not applicable
2008	2,222	100 %	Not applicable
2007	3,151	100 %	Not applicable

Calculation of the indicator: Compared to 2009, there was an increase of 0.05 % in 2010. Compared to 2008, there was a reduction of 0.05 % in 2009. Compared to 2007, there was no change in 2008.

Interpretation: This indicator measures the presence of potato brown rot and/or ring rot within the Belgian plant production chain. An increase of this indicator, i.e. an increase in the percentage of compliant samples, therefore implies an improvement in the plant health situation in Belgium.

Part of the chain to which the indicator applies: Primary plant production, plant and plant product trading (including exports), plant propagation.

Type of plant or plant product: Seed plants, table plants.

Category: Control.

Justification for the selection of this indicator: The presence on the Belgian territory of harmful quarantine organisms such as potato brown rot and ring rot can be extremely detrimental, economically speaking, to plant and plant product production. It is therefore essential to maintain/improve the phytosanitary situation by verifying the absence of these organisms.

Additional information: In the EU, *Ralstonia solanacearum* is mainly found in potatoes (*Solanum tuberosum*), tomatoes (*Lycopersicon esculentum*) and woody nightshade *Solanum dulcamara*. *R. solanacearum* is widespread in tropical, subtropical and warm temperature areas throughout the world. In the EU, a "low temperature" strain is adapted to cooler climates in the highlands of the tropics and in the Mediterranean area. Its occurrence has now been reported from temperate zones, and in particular from a number of European countries in the 1990s. Due to the existence of various strains, this bacterium can be found throughout the world.

The bacterium can spread in soil, in which it survives for varying periods of time, and in irrigation and drainage water. The entry of the bacterium into plants is by way of injured roots, stem wounds or through stomata. Within the plant, the bacteria move in vascular bundles (including the tubers for potatoes, which has the most significant potential economic impact), a process which is accelerated by higher temperatures.

The first visible symptom on potatoes is the wilting of the leaves at the ends of the branches during the heat of the day with recovery at night: eventually plants fail to recover and die. In terms of the tubers, a bacterial ooze often emerges from the eyes and stem-end attachment of infected tubers.

Further information relating to potato brown rot and ring rot is available at the following address: http://www.eppo.org/QUARANTINE/bacteria/Ralstonia_solanacearum/PSDMSO_ds.pdf.

In the EU, *Clavibacter michiganensis* subsp. *sepedonicus* can only be found naturally in potatoes. This bacterium can be found in the EU, America (North, central and South) and in Asia. The temperature optimum for the growth of *C. michiganensis* subsp. *sepedonicus* is relatively low (21°C) and is mainly confined to cooler areas of the world.

After a diseased potato is planted, the bacteria multiply very rapidly and pass along the vascular strands into the stems and petioles. From there they reach the roots and maturing daughter tubers, sometimes within eight weeks of planting, thereby representing a significant economic impact.

The symptoms shown on infected plants are rather variable. They usually appear late in the growing season. First symptoms of wilting develop in the lower leaves, before spreading to the entire plant. In terms of the tubers, wilting of the vascular ring occurs, which becomes progressively yellow then light brown (= wet bacterial rot).

This bacterium is spread by direct tuber to tuber contact or indirectly via machinery, storage areas or other materials, which have been in contact with the contaminated tubers.

Other information relating to potato ring rot is available at the following address:

http://www.eppo.org/QUARANTINE/bacteria/Clavibacter_m_sepedonicus/CORBSE_ds.pdf.

Legal framework:

1. Council Directive 2000/29/EC of 8/05/2000 on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community.
2. Royal decree of 19/11/1987 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products.
3. Royal decree of 10/08/2005 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products.
4. Ministerial decree of 4/07/1996 establishing the conditions under which certain harmful organisms, plants, plant products or other objects listed in appendices I to V of the Royal Decree of 3 May 1994 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products, may be introduced or moved within the Community or certain protected zones thereof for trial or scientific purposes or for work on varietal selection.
5. Ministerial Decree of 14/02/2000 setting out the measures to prevent the spread of *Ralstonia solanacearum* (Smith) Yabuuchi *et al.*
6. Ministerial Decree of 30/08/1999 on the control of *Ralstonia solanacearum* (Smith) Yabuuchi *et al.*
7. Ministerial Decree of 3/11/1994 on the control of bacterial ring rot of potato (*Clavibacter michiganensis* (Smith) Davis *et al.* spp. *sepedonicus* (Spieckermann et Kotthoff) Davis *et al.*).
8. Commission directive 2006/63/EC modifying Annexes II to VII of the Council Directive 98/57/EEC of 20/07/1998 on the control of *Ralstonia solanacearum* (Smith) Yabuuchi *et al.*
9. Commission Directive 2006/56/EC of 12 June 2006 modifying the annexes of Council Directive 93/85/EEC of 4 October 1993 on the control of bacterial ring rot of potato.

Does the indicator meet the set criteria?:

- Measureable (availability of quantitative data)
- Independent (no overlap between respective indicators)
- Reliable (bias sensitivity)
- Availability of information contained in existing reports or documents
- Relevancy with respect to the health situation of plant production
- Clear interpretation
- Sustainable
- The body of indicators must be representative of the plant and plant product production chain

Comments: Uncertain relevant data extraction The statistical data listed for year 'a' actually relate to the previous crop year 'a-1' (= from 1st June of year 'a-1' to 31 May of year 'a'), and are in accordance with the statistical data published in the FASFC annual activity reports and with the requirements on the reporting of findings to the European Commission.

Explanatory notes to the results: In 2009 (= 2008 crop year), the findings for brown rot were 100% consistent with respect to seed potatoes but 1 case of contamination was confirmed for one batch of farmer's seed potatoes. All measures required to ensure the complete eradication of the bacterium were taken: destruction (through biomethanisation) or safe processing (for example into mashed potato, at the end of the working day and ensuring decontamination of the production line, waste incineration and water treatment).

PHI11: <i>Pospiviroidae</i>			
Description: The annual percentage of compliant results in relation to the control of <i>pospiviroidae</i> within the framework of the FASFC control plan.			
Results:			
Year	Number of samples	% conformity	Limit
2010	194	67.0 %	Not applicable
2009	143	99.3 %	Not applicable
2008	138	97.1 %	Not applicable
2007	248	73 %	Not applicable
Calculation of the indicator: Compared to 2009, there was a reduction of 32.53 % in 2010. Compared to 2008, there was an increase of 2.27 % in 2009. Compared to 2007, there was an increase of 33.01 % in 2008.			
Interpretation: This indicator measures the presence of <i>pospiviroidae</i> within the Belgian plant production chain. An increase of this indicator, i.e. an increase in the percentage of compliant samples, therefore implies an improvement in the plant health situation in Belgium.			
Part of the chain to which the indicator applies: Primary plant production, plant and plant product trading (including imports/exports), plant propagation.			
Type of plant or plant product: Ornamental plants, tomato plants, seed potatoes			
Category: Control.			
Justification for the selection of this indicator: The presence on the Belgian territory of harmful quarantine organisms such as potato spindle tuber viroid can be extremely detrimental, economically speaking, to plant and plant product production. It is therefore essential to maintain/improve the plant health situation by verifying the absence of this organism.			
Additional information: In the EU, the <i>Potato spindle tuber viroid (PSTVd)</i> is mainly found in potatoes as well as tomatoes and other <i>Solanum</i> spp (<i>Solanaceae</i> crops). This viroid is widespread around the world but is considered as absent from the EU despite several recently reported cases. Aphids, <i>Macrosiphum euphorbiae</i> and <i>Myzus persicae</i> in particular, as well as other European insects (<i>Eupteryx atropunctata</i> , <i>Empoasca flavescens</i> , <i>Lygus pratensis</i> and <i>Leptinotarsa decemlineata</i>) have been implicated as probable vectors but the disease can be mechanically transmitted easily through contact between healthy and diseased plants, tractor wheels and tools etc. On potatoes, a clockwise phyllotaxy of the foliage may be apparent when the plants are viewed from directly above. The foliage is spindly and very upright, often being a darker green than normal and slightly rugose. Plants are stunted. The tubers are small (and hence having a potential significant economic impact), elongated, cylindrical, spindle or dumbbell shaped, with prominent eyes evenly distributed over the tuber. Sprouting is slower than in healthy tubers. Further information relating to potato spindle tuber viroid is available at the following address: http://www.eppo.org/QUARANTINE/virus/PSTVd/PSTVD0_ds.pdf .			
Legal framework:			
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Council Directive 2000/29/EC of 8/05/2000 on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community. 2. Royal decree of 19/11/1987 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products. 3. Royal decree of 10/08/2005 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products. 4. Ministerial decree of 4/07/1996 establishing the conditions under which certain harmful organisms, plants, plant products or other objects listed in appendices I to V of the Royal Decree of 3 May 1994 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products, may be introduced or moved within the Community or certain protected zones thereof for trial or scientific purposes or for work on varietal selection. 5. Commission Decision 2007/410/EC of 12/06/2007 on measures to prevent the introduction into and the spread within the Community of Potato spindle tuber viroid. 			
Does the indicator meet the set criteria?:			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Measureable (availability of quantitative data) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Independent (no overlap between respective indicators) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reliable (bias sensitivity) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Availability of information contained in existing reports or documents <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Relevancy with respect to the health situation of plant production			

- Clear interpretation
- Sustainable
- The body of indicators must be representative of the plant and plant product production chain

Comments: As from 2010 only, the parameter "*PSTVd*" has been replaced in the FASFC control plan by the "*pospiviroidae*" parameter. The following viroids have since been researched: *Citrus exocortis viroid*, *Chrysanthemum stunt viroid*, *Columnnea latent viroid*, *Mexican papita viroid*, *Tomato apical stunt viroid*, *Tomato chlorotic dwarf viroid* and *Tomato planta macho viroid*.

Explanatory notes to the results: In 2009, no contamination by *PSTVd* was detected in Belgian companies. During monitoring, other viroids – closely related to *PSTVd* – were found. As a precautionary measure and following consultation with the EC, the contaminated plants were destroyed.

In 2008, during the monitoring process, 4 contaminated batches of *Solanum jasminoides* (climbing solanaceae) were found at 3 farms. Three of these batches were destroyed, the fourth was shipped back to its Italian supplier. The number of contaminated batches found has dropped significantly compared to previous years.

In 2007, out of the 248 samples taken in Belgian establishments, 67 tested positive. This concerned ornamental plants only.

PHI12: <i>Diabrotica virgifera</i> Le Conte (Corn rootworm)			
Description: The annual percentage of compliant samples tested for corn rootworm (<i>Diabrotica virgifera</i> Le Conte) within the framework of the FASFC control plan.			
Results:			
Year	Number of samples	% conformity	Limit
2010	421 traps	100 %	Not applicable
2009	423 traps	100 %	Not applicable
2008	467 traps	100 %	Not applicable
2007	512 traps	100 %	Not applicable
Calculation of the indicator: Compared to 2009, there was no change in 2010. Compared to 2008, there was no change in 2009. Compared to 2007, there was no change in 2008.			
Interpretation: This indicator measures the presence of corn rootworm within the Belgian plant production chain. An increase of this indicator, i.e. an increase in the percentage of compliant samples, therefore implies an improvement in the plant health situation in Belgium.			
Part of the chain to which the indicator applies: Primary plant production (corn crop), plant propagation.			
Type of plant or plant product: Corn crops (traps).			
Category: Control.			
Justification for the selection of this indicator: The presence on the Belgian territory of harmful quarantine organisms such as corn rootworm can be extremely detrimental, economically speaking, to plant and plant product production. It is therefore essential to maintain/improve the plant health situation by verifying the presence or absence of this organism.			
Additional information: <i>Diabrotica virgifera</i> Le Conte mainly attacks corn (<i>Zea mays</i>), the larvae feed on the roots and the adults feed on the leaves and silks. This insect originates from North America but can also be found in Central America and Central Europe. Tunnels in maize roots, giving the plants a greater tendency to lodge, are a characteristic symptom, though they may be due to other species. Adult feeding does not cause any particularly characteristic symptom. Within Europe, <i>D. virgifera</i> is mainly spread by adult flight. It is also possible that it could be carried by consignments of maize cobs or green maize. Further information relating to corn rootworm is available at the following address: http://www.eppo.org/QUARANTINE/insects/Diabrotica_barber/DIABSP_ds.pdf .			
Legal framework:			
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Council Directive 2000/29/EC of 8/05/2000 on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community. 2. Royal decree of 19/11/1987 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products. 3. Royal decree of 10/08/2005 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products. 4. Ministerial decree of 4/07/1996 establishing the conditions under which certain harmful organisms, plants, plant products or other objects listed in appendices I to V of the Royal Decree of 3/05/1994 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products, may be introduced or moved within the Community or certain protected zones thereof for trial or scientific purposes or for work on varietal selection. 5. Ministerial Decree of 14/04/2005 on the temporary measures for controlling corn rootworm, <i>Diabrotica virgifera</i> Le Conte. 6. Decision 2003/766/EC on emergency measures to prevent the spread within the Community of <i>Diabrotica virgifera</i> Le Conte. 7. Commission Recommendation of 11/08/2006 on containment programmes to limit the further spread of <i>Diabrotica virgifera</i> Le Conte in Community areas where its presence is confirmed. 			
Does the indicator meet the set criteria?:			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Measureable (availability of quantitative data) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Independent (no overlap between respective indicators) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reliable (bias sensitivity) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Availability of information contained in existing reports or documents <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Relevancy with respect to the health situation of plant production <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Clear interpretation			

Sustainable

The body of indicators must be representative of the plant and plant product production chain

Comments: A compliant result relates to a trap in which corn rootworm was not identified. The traps are dispersed throughout Belgium, on account of the risks, and particularly around ports and airports and major routes of commerce.

Explanatory notes to the results: -

PHI13: <i>Phytophthora ramorum</i> (Sudden oak death)			
Description: The annual percentage of compliant samples tested for sudden oak death (<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>) within the framework of the FASFC control plan.			
Results:			
Year	Number of samples	% conformity	Limit
2010	226	91.6 %	Not applicable
2009	244	75.8 %	Not applicable
2008	277	78.3 %	Not applicable
2007	206	81 %	Not applicable
Calculation of the indicator: Compared to 2009, there was an increase of 20.84 % in 2010. Compared to 2008, there was a reduction of 3.19 % in 2009. Compared to 2007, there was a reduction of 3.33 % in 2008.			
Interpretation: This indicator measures the presence of sudden oak death within the Belgian plant production chain. An increase of this indicator, i.e. an increase in the percentage of compliant samples, therefore implies an improvement in the plant health situation in Belgium.			
Part of the chain to which the indicator applies: Primary plant production, plant and plant product trading (including imports/exports), plant propagation, green spaces and forests.			
Type of plant or plant product: ornamental crops.			
Category: Control.			
Justification for the selection of this indicator: The presence on the Belgian territory of harmful quarantine organisms such as sudden oak death can be extremely detrimental, economically speaking, to plant and plant product production. It is therefore essential to maintain/improve the plant health situation by verifying the absence of this organism.			
Additional information: <i>Phytophthora ramorum</i> is a species of mould that is found in the EU and USA (mainly in California), but its origin is still unknown. In the EU, <i>P. ramorum</i> has mainly been found in <i>Rhododendron</i> and <i>Viburnum</i> , but was recently isolated from <i>Arbutus</i> , <i>Camellia</i> , <i>Hamamelis</i> , <i>Kalmia</i> , <i>Leucothoe</i> , <i>Magnolia</i> , <i>Pieris</i> , <i>Larix</i> and <i>Syringa</i> . In particular the infections detected in <i>Larix</i> have become widespread in the United Kingdom. In shrubs, the main symptoms are necrosis and/or discolouration of the stems and branches, leaf spots, the browning or blackening of the buds and wilting of the stems and shoots. In trees (mainly the beech family), the disease is characterised by the development of cankers that are sometimes bleeding usually found on the base of trunks in a dark brown to bituminous black colour. The wilting then the death of the tree occurs when the cankers girdle the trunk. The infection occurs through zoospores, sporangia and chlamydospores. As with other <i>Phytophthora</i> diseases, it is common for the disease to be transmitted by plants and infected soils. Further information relating to sudden oak death is available at the following address: http://www.eppo.org/QUARANTINE/Alert_List/fungi/PHYTRA.htm .			
Legal framework:			
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Council Directive 2000/29/EC of 8/05/2000 on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community. 2. Royal decree of 19/11/1987 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products. 3. Royal decree of 10/08/2005 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products. 4. Ministerial decree of 4/07/1996 establishing the conditions under which certain harmful organisms, plants, plant products or other objects listed in appendices I to V of the Royal Decree of 3/05/1994 on the control of organisms harmful to plants and plant products, may be introduced or moved within the Community or certain protected zones thereof for trial or scientific purposes or for work on varietal selection. 5. By Commission decision 2002/757/EC of 19/09/2002 the Member States were provisionally required to take emergency phytosanitary measures to prevent the introduction and spread within the Community of <i>Phytophthora ramorum</i> Werres, De Cock & Man in 't Veld sp. November. 			
Does the indicator meet the set criteria?:			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Measureable (availability of quantitative data) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Independent (no overlap between respective indicators) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reliable (bias sensitivity) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Availability of information contained in existing reports or documents			

Relevancy with respect to the health situation of plant production

Clear interpretation

Sustainable

The body of indicators must be representative of the plant and plant product production chain

Comments: This indicator actually represents the percentage of companies that are not infected in relation to the total number of inspected companies.

Explanatory notes to the results: In 2010, contamination was found within 8 companies - representing an improvement compared with 2009. In public green spaces, 239 sites were subject to inspection; no contamination was observed.

In 2009, the 15 companies in which contamination was found were required to destroy the contaminated plants and host plants within a 2 metre radius. The host plants located within a radius of 10 metres of the outbreak underwent quarantine measures and a regular review of the presence of symptoms over a 3 month period. In public green spaces, 121 sites underwent an inspection; no contamination was found.

In 2008, quarantine measures were imposed on 24 farms in which contamination had been found. In public green spaces, a contamination of *Rhododendron* was identified in 5 different places; appropriate control measures were implemented. The number of sites in which a contamination has been found has increased in relation to 2007.

In 2007, in the 19 farms in which contamination was identified, quarantine measures were imposed. In public green spaces, *Rhododendron* plants recently planted and affected were also discovered. Appropriate control measures were imposed. No symptoms were reported in the surrounding area.